

Conference Abstract

Cultural Considerations in Leadership and Performance Management

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Abstract

In the context of performance management, this working paper explores the relations between cultural characteristics and leadership styles. Understanding how various cultural frameworks impact the implementation and effectiveness of performance management becomes increasingly crucial as organizations operate on a global scale (Carol and Florah 2019, Agrawal 2019).

“How do cultural differences influence leadership approaches, and what impact does this have on the success of performance management practices in a multicultural environment?”

Addressing this inquiry, this work aims to explore the influence of cultural differences on leadership approaches and their subsequent effects on the successful implementation of performance management systems.

To answer this question, we will thoroughly examine different dimensions of culture that may affect the design, implementation, and outcomes of performance management initiatives through a comprehensive review of current literature, multicultural leadership models, and case studies (Hofstede 2001).

The primary objective is to illuminate the challenges arising from diverse cultural perspectives and potential obstacles in achieving optimal performance management outcomes within a heterogeneous environment. Furthermore, the paper suggests

employing effective strategies and innovative leadership approaches to successfully navigate these cultural challenges in a way that positively impacts performance (Detert et al. 2000, Rhodes and Brown 2005).

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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